

Articles series, part 1: Tolerances in implant dentistry. Insights upon the root of the tolerances produced during modern production processes

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Abstract

Tolerances is an essential part of the mechanical productions. It should be considered in the context of every mechanical evaluation. In this series, we want to shade the light on the effect of the issue ion the mechanical performances.

Keywords: Tolerances, mechanical engineering, CNC production, Milling, Servo motors,

Introduction

Every mechanical engineering knows that the drawings whether 2d or 3d will have a mismatch with the actual produced part whatever the production process is (subtractive or additive, casting, sinteringetc.) (1). This mismatch had been incorporated initially in the modern design process as the concept of tolerances. Tolerances is the accepted range of this dimensional mismatching.

TYPES OF TOLERANCES

Figure 1 Mechanical tolerances should be considered in any mechanical evaluation

Dental implant machining is totally different from the machining of the abutment. Most of the machined features of the abutment are external but in the case of the implant these features are internal. This is one of the reasons behind selection of the hardest Titanium alloy for the abutment and the softer alloy for the implant.

We have 2 types of machining:

- External machining where the tools had better rigidity and the surface finishing will be good
- Internal machining where the tool will have less optimal factors that will produce less optimal results

Anyhow surface finishing is determined by many factors. (2)

Figure 2 The lines of machining are evident

The lines in the figure 1 indicate the clearly difference between the reality and the computerized designs. The inner hole of the dental abutments is small where these abutments is mostly manufactured from highly strong material grade 5 Titanium with machining properties of high strength stainless steel.

Figure 3 the surface finishing criteria should be chosen as an important evaluating objective measure

Figure 4 The surface finishing of the Italian Macco abutment on the right and the Turkish Detech abutment on the left indicate the machining criteria clearly

Even with single continuous surface we have macing marks Macco on the left vs Detech on the right, both are good implant system, but the manufacturing process are the same. This is external machining. Hex finishing and sizes are clearly different. (3)

Turing macing had better center and the outer shape will be always perfect circle in cross section, but in case of milling center we will end with non-circular shape. This is the concept behind the refusal of the abutment base produced with the dental CAD CAM systems.

Figure 5 This is the simplest form of motorized computerized stage

The CNC whether milling or turning had these components

- The motor (4)

Even with the best servo motor, we have some uncertainty about the positional accuracy. Each motor used in the CNC machines is stepper motor that is used to control the motion of the stage in a certain axis.

Figure 6 The stepper motor had predefined steady robust angular movements

Figure 7 The encoder is an addition to the stepper motor to convert it to a servomotor

Figure 8 Even the electrical processing lag could affect the CNC accuracy and affect the tolerances

- The rail will have lesser effect on the tolerances, but it will absolutely have an effect at the end. (5)

Figure 9 The linear rail had moving balls and tolerances between these balls. The stiffest part of the rail could even have some sort of deflection when the tool cut from the stock

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- The moving screw (5), even with the best ball screw are used, we have a certain tolerance. This will be appeared in the positional inaccuracies of the positioning of the cutting tool when do forward and reward movement of the cutting stage

Figure 10 Nothing is absolute in the mechanical productions

- The tool itself (6), this especially appear in the turning center where almost all implants are produces by this method of machining. Changing the cutting tool to cut different features will have different story to be told.

Figure 11 The geometry of the tools clearly had some tolerances

Figure 12 The positional sensor will tell the machine about part of the cutting tool but not the other parts or sides of the tool. Cutting tool will have vibration that will affect the surface finishing

- The stage that holds the sample to be cut will affect the tolerances especially in the Swiss lathe used exclusively to produce dental implants.

Figure 13 Swiss lath are used to produced part with tight tolerances

Figure 14 Milling center could not produce a perfect cylinder as the production of the circular motion will be produced by moving in the X and Y axis, while in the case of turning we will get a perfect circle at the outer or inner side of the part in each time.

Figure 15 One of the most important issues is the input for the CNC machine. The shape on the right is engineering shape, but the other 3 shapes are triangulated that will absolutely affected by the resolution and will not represent a true circle in cross section

Figure 16 G-code is the translation of the 3D shape into numbers that lead the machine to the proposed position to cut the desired amount for subtractive production

Figure 17 The difference between the rigidity and the stiffness of the CNC milling machines that used in the dental laboratories and the CNC turning machine that is used in the factories to produced parts are enormous and incomparable

Any movement of any stage of the CNC will not return to its initial position

Methods

We had compared 5 different implant systems to get an idea about the tolerances

Figure 18 The tolerances in the simplest aides to be machined will indicate the tolerances in the other more difficult part such as the inner side of the implants

We had compared the hex of

- Mode narrow platform
- Mode implant regular platform
- NucleOSS T6
- Evos short implant
- Alliance one-piece implants

We had compared 5 samples using professional industrial grade micrometer screw gauge

Figure 19 This is professional grade micrometer

Each hex had 6 sides thus we have 3 reading for each piece.

Results and discussions

We had 2 sets of readings

- 3 readings for each piece
- Reading between the different pieces from the same sample entity

The results were

- For mode narrow platform abutment, the maximum difference in the same sample was 18 microns, while minimum and maximum values across all the sample from this group was 88 microns
- For the mode regular platform abutment, the maximum difference in the same sample was 13 microns, while minimum and maximum values across all the sample from this group was 20 microns
- For the NucleOSS system abutment, the maximum difference in the same sample was 15 microns, while minimum and maximum values across all the sample from this group was 18 microns.
- For evos short implant abutment, the maximum difference in the same sample was 8 microns, while minimum and maximum values across all the sample from this group was 9 microns.
- For anker implant system hex, the maximum difference in the same sample was 5 microns, while minimum and maximum values across all the sample from this group was 6 microns

The current reported tolerances are less than the reported in previous study as the new machining capabilities had been witnessed huge advancements (7)

The difference between the measurements of the same sample due to retraction of the cutting tool and rotation of the cut sample. This difference is much less than the maximum and minimum across different samples from the same group due to the addition to the grasping tool on the sample positioning. (8)

We should emphasize upon the fact that the machining of the external hex is much mode easier than the machining of the deep hex of the implant as well as that the machining of different features such as the cone in not an easy job in the case measurement as it need advanced machines such as CMM not a simple micrometer gauge. These findings shade the light on the important aspect of implant evaluation base on simple reliable method of measurement. We should know that these readings are just for a single feature of the implant, the hex which had been produced by simple motion of the CNC milling machine. To characterize the tolerances more we should use advanced tool such as CMM, as we already said (9)

Figure 20 CMM are used to characterize the dimensions of complex shapes and geometries

Figure 21 Tolerances, simply means that we may have shorter or wider abutment or any combination with possibility of the this at any side or feature of the machined part

Figure 22 The mismatch could be happened at any region as different region machining need retraction of the tool from a certain position and attain a new position

In the next paper we will discuss the issue of the implants systems that had multiple contacts between the implant and abutment at different levels, simply the contact is not a single continuous region

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.